

BM-5102 Organisational Behaviour

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Reflective Critique Report

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Before taking Master

During my years in UBD as a bachelor of degree in Geography and Development student, I have always fascinated myself in taking Business accounting as my major in UBD. However, I was unfortunately unable to get into the SBE programme due to not acquiring enough points for the faculty. Thus I was then transferred to FASS faculty taking Geography and Development. Throughout the year during my UBD degree life, I managed to gather a substantial amount of knowledge in regards to developing the country, and then realise that this has been the course for my career which involves the way to move forward into a developed country. May it be in the form of rising GDP of the country and or raising the standard of living of the people.

However, having finished my degree in Geography and Development in 2019 and graduated in 2020. I tried my best getting into work in line with my major, but was rejected by three departments under the Ministry of Development. During my final year, I was working with Fuel'd Restaurant to this day I am still working at that restaurant. Having told the CEO of Fuel'd regarding my situation having no luck in finding work related to my major, she then suggested pursuing my studies rather than waiting for a work opportunity.

This then becomes part of the motivation in taking Master in Management. With having learned OB, we first touch upon the understanding of Motivation, and this part of the paper will then be focused on the main motivation in pursuing my Masters Degree.

Motivation may come in the form of a distraction, for example, talking with co-workers, or with playing the computer. This can be seen as a distraction, however, it can also be a motivation where ideas are gathered by talking with co-workers or having spent a few minutes with computers. This is actually where I personally got motivated into taking masters.

There are few drawbacks to taking master in my own opinion, however, the good it would do for future reference may out-weight the drawbacks. To put into visual presentation, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs is suitable. The model is a psychological theory of motivation where a person has 5 needs. Which includes physiology, comfort, love and belonging, esteem and self-actualization. These 5 levels are what motivates a person to take a master, to think about what I can accomplish, and the doors that can be opened by completing and taking a Master in Management.

In the case of physiology, I substitute it for psychology, while by taking master, I would not feel left behind by having my friend that took Geography and Development to pursue Master in Management as well so that I have a support in doing this. ii) Security needs, as I said the doors would be open to me, needing to acquire a Master's degree in Management, mainly in the Employment Department, especially where I currently work, the CEO has asked me to work with them if and when I finish my Master. iii) Love and belonging, making my parents proud of me and having to be able to have a sense of relation with my parents, because they are also the holder of the Master. iv) Self-esteem, again with appreciation from my parents, being able to complete my master's degree, and having to learn to be a 'manager' and what is the right and wrong way to run a business. And finally v) Self-actualization, being able to be proud of myself as I've been dreaming of achieving this level of education and not drowning in the shadows of other people. These are the things that keep me motivated, it's not what I have right now that

motivates me, it's the things that I will accomplish later in the near future that keeps a person, like myself, motivated in UBD as well as working.

During Master

Having attended classes during the COVID pandemic, it has been a whole different experience, compared to what I am used to which is having a physical class setting. With the virtual classes becoming a norm, there are few drawbacks, and in my own experience, it has been a tough one. Being in a virtual environment leads to me having to wake up and expecting the class to start owning that it would start like a regular class, however, there are some delays in the class, mainly issues on connecting with the lecturer on a student and lecturer relationship. I find it quite unsuccessful as I am unable to ask questions that I normally would do in a regular class, mainly because knowing myself would be present in another student's screen which makes me uncomfortable. There are also issue with technical difficult, granted that this virtual class has start this year, and there are those lecturer that are unable to coupe with the virtual learning experience quite yet and that is understandable but being as it is, it is a major drawback is connecting the student with what is meant to be taught in said class. This later made it quite difficult due to the pandemic, it has made the module to get 100% marks that are based on coursework and assignments.

Moving on to the module relating to organizational behaviour, I briefly research on the subject matter and can agree with an article published by Mukuka (2020), that organizational behaviour is important in making sure the success of the company as well as the treatment of the staff are made sure to be fair and humane. This is in terms of having people motivation of the staff to insure efficiency of an organization, as well as to ensure the office characteristics, being that each individual staff is well aware and are comfortable with their own standards, knowing that standards ann characteristic of each individual staff is important and was taught most part of that in the module.

Regarding the coursework, we were given two research projects; a group case project which includes presentation and report, and the second one being an individual assessment analysis paper. When it comes to the research project, a group of four people in my group have decided to tackle and research regarding the issues and challenges of the halal industry, in terms of education, training and development. At first this research was like any other, which has the same planning stage, which includes, planning for the paper, coming up with interview questions, filling out ethics forms, and finally having to wait for approval on the ethics' form. There was a few delay when it comes to the approval of the form, while waiting, our group took the initiative to go out to every relevant Halal industry market in Brunei, which included Universiti Sultan Sharif Ali, a religious university, Brunei Halal, Brunei's Halal certification provider as well as the Ministry of Health together with Ministry of Religious Affair. Four weeks into waiting for the form, there has been changes in the approval of the form, mainly because there has been an increase in the number of people conducting research and it then makes it difficult for future researchers to conduct legitimate research for the betterment of the country other than for results. Thus makes all our groups' effort of finding and talking with representatives of UNISSA, Brunei Halal and MOH as well as MORA to be a waste. However,

our group completely understood the situation and decided to switch the case study paper into a systematic literature review paper.

Second assessment was the Individual Analysis paper, which I wrote on the relationship between motivation of staff and management strategies. This was the same case for the group case study paper where I had to switch the paper for a research paper into a systematic literature review paper. When it comes to systematic literature review paper, there is a major drawback for a perfect systematic literature review paper which is, it takes six months to two years in order to create a valid systematic literature review paper and require to analyse between 40 to more articles which is needed to compare and contrast each articles with one another. For most of the students, we were given three weeks to complete which was quite challenging but in return we did our best in doing what was needed from us by our lecturer.

Outcome of the modules as well as Masters as a whole by far

After finishing one challenging semester, I do believe that this is the right path for me in order to pursue further to achieve my career goals which is to be a manager or higher in the place that I am currently working at, hopefully by the time I do managed to finish and graduate from Masters of Management is that I would be employee is something I am looking forward for which is on the recruiting department. Comparing my four year degree experience, it is truly nothing compared to one semester of taking master plus in a pandemic mode difficulty. Regarding the module of organization behaviour, the module is important for me as it teaches me in why an organization behaves the way they do, how they have managed to create a culture of their own, which has a unique culture than any other organization. Finally this module is sure to be beneficial for me when being in the HR department under recruitment as hopefully, I would be able to tell if an applicant is suitable for the culture of the organization.

References

Mukuka, M. (2020). *(PDF) Significance of organisational behaviour*. ResearchGate. Retrieved 18 November 2020, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338630653_Significance_of_organisational_behaviour.